

Academic Service System Development Using Enterprise Architecture Modeling

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Abstract: As an enterprise engaged in the education sector, it has become an obligation for universities to provide good services, especially academic services, using information technology and information systems. Academic services are administrative-technical work carried out both physically and logically offered by academics or admissions to students and other academic communities. In building an academic service system, careful planning is needed, because one of the factors in the failure of system implementation is the lack of good planning and by business needs, therefore it is necessary to create an enterprise architecture that will produce a blueprint that can be a guide and reference for activities academic information system planning and development services. The framework used to build this academic service system modeling is to use the TOGAF framework. The results of this study indicate that by implementing the TOGAF framework phase of architecture vision, business architecture, information systems architecture, and technology architecture, has resulted in improvements or solutions to improve academic service performance so that the problem of the absence of information systems in the organization can be solved with this architecture.

Keywords: Academic Service System, Architecture Enterprise, Collage, Framework, TOGAF

I. INTRODUCTION

University is an enterprise engaged in the education sector. Indonesia has 4664 tertiary institutions (forlap.dikti.go.id, 2020) spread across 34 provinces. With the increasing number of universities, it will cause increasingly fierce competition, both regarding service and achievement. A good strategy to improve the quality of tertiary institutions is to provide the best service to university stakeholders, namely prospective students, students, lecturers, employees, and alumni.

To be able to provide good services, along with the times and the increasing needs, then a university should consider improving services using information technology and information systems. The use of information technology is very beneficial when applied in service to the community. Through this development, information technology is no longer just a technological tool to improve the efficiency of internal processes but becomes an important part of value creation that grows until a new source of competitive advantage [1]. Higher education institutions must take anticipatory steps to face increasingly competitive competition and are responsible for improving all aspects of their services that can be applied using information technology and information systems.

There are a variety of business processes carried out at a tertiary institution, namely academic services, financial services, library services, and so on. Academic services are efforts undertaken by tertiary institutions to provide convenience to the fulfillment of a student's needs relating to academic activities. According to [19], academic services included in administrative-technical work carried out both physically and logically, and services offered by academics or admissions to students and other academics, basically do not result in ownership. So, it can be concluded that academic services are a series of activities that are visible and invisible from the university to the academicians, especially students who carry out a series of academic processes that support student lecturing activities while studying in college.

Universities still have problems with academic services that cause dissatisfaction for students. Academic service problems often faced by students include (1) the registration system that is late and has not yet applied technology and information systems because it is still done with the recording system in the registration book, (2) the making of study plan cards is still done manually by submitting the plan card study directly to the staff in charge of managing the study plan card, (3) student study results have not been managed using a special system that causes an ineffective work

system and minimal data security because it has not been managed in a database, (4) the graduation registration system is still manual that is, students submit registration files to the staff and then do the data collection without using an integrated system with a database.

Based on the problems that occur in academic services, there is one conclusion that causes the academic services that have not been maximized at a tertiary institution, namely not yet implementing information technology and information systems that are integrated with databases. In fact, with the development of technology, it should be a university to leave the old way and move on to a new system. Especially now that the world is facing a coronavirus pandemic that requires academic staff to work from home and students to learn from home. If academic workers do not implement information systems that are centralized in one system, then the risk of data loss and data redundancy becomes greater. Therefore, in a university, a system for academic services are needed so that academic activities can continue to run optimally. Workers must manage new information, solve unstructured problems, and replace manual activities into activities that are integrated with the system [2].

In building an academic service system, careful planning is needed, because one factor in the failure of system implementation is the lack of good planning and following business needs. Likewise, what happened in tertiary institutions, the development of an academic service system sporadically based on spontaneous needs without going through the stages of good planning and being partial is one of the causes of the failure [18]. Successful planning is how to meet the current and future strategic needs of the organization [3]. It is very important to do a careful planning and following the company's vision in making IS/IT, which covers all business processes in the company. So that in the future, the company can compete with companies engaged in the same field. Therefore, to minimize the failure and ineffectiveness of the system to be built it is necessary to create an enterprise architecture of academic information systems, which is in line with the needs of the organization.

Enterprise architecture is a hierarchical way to describe how information systems, business processes, and people are involved in all organizational functions [4], [20], [5]. The strong architecture of IT systems will provide better communication facilities between organizations and related stakeholders [6]. Enterprise architecture also translates the organization's vision and mission into operational reality and utilizes technology to improve public sector service delivery systems, so that the process of sharing information between organizations will be more efficient [7], [21], [8]. Architectural design provides a blueprint for defining the structure and business processes of an organization. This research is focused on designing an enterprise architecture that will provide a blueprint to be a guideline and reference for academic information systems planning and development activities that can support the goals and objectives of the organization, taking into account the needs and business processes at the tertiary institutions.

In building an enterprise architecture (EA) plan, a framework is needed to manage innovations in the company and can be used to develop architecture properly [17]. The framework that can be used to design enterprise architecture is the TOGAF (The Open Group Architecture Framework) Framework. TOGAF is a framework for building enterprise architecture that provides a comprehensive approach to designing, planning, implementing, and managing enterprise information architectures. TOGAF is an Open Group standard that is widely used by the world's leading organizations to improve business efficiency. TOGAF has also become the most prominent and reliable Enterprise Architecture standard, providing detailed methods on how to build and manage and implement enterprise architecture and information systems so that they can become recommendations for the development of integrated IS/IT.

Previous research has been carried out on enterprise architecture utilities for records and archive specialists [9]. This research shows how records and archive specialists can utilize enterprise architecture that is included in the systems thinking approach, to fulfill their professional mandate. This research focuses on TOGAF but has not yet explained how the architecture design implementation of the object under study. Therefore, in this study the author wants to explain how the implementation of the TOGAF framework in designing an architecture in the academic service sector in tertiary institutions.

The purpose of this research is to produce a blueprint that explains how the elements of IT and information management work together as a whole, so that this research is expected to provide guidance and direction for the development of academic service systems at a tertiary institution.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Enterprise architecture compiles all relevant components to describe business processes in an enterprise, including the processes used for the development of enterprise architecture. There is research on the elements in the development of enterprise architecture [10] and the principles applied in the development of enterprise architecture [11]. So that in the development of a system, it is not done spontaneously but has a structured basis and guidelines.

In a previous study, [12] the paper described creating an information system for evaluating the performance of sports teams, which developed a mobile version of a web application. Before doing system development, the author has made the interface design and system architect. However, in the development of this system, analysis has not been carried out using a specific framework to adjust the needs of users with business processes that are running. It would be better if before building the system design information system architecture is done to avoid the failure of system implementation.

The analytical approach for enterprise information system architecture to align business process requirements has been previously studied [13]. Based on this research it can be concluded that enterprise architecture provides a well-developed approach to aligning organizations and the use of technology to optimize work in an organization. The analysis in this study shows that there is a strong relationship between enterprise architecture, enterprise information systems, and business process companies. If among these three aspects experience disharmony, it can have an impact on organizational performance. Therefore, it is very important to harmonize between enterprise architecture, enterprise information systems, and business processes, especially in this case it is on academic services in tertiary institutions.

TOGAF is an enterprise architecture design framework that is widely applied by researchers as an industry standard that defines three levels of architecture, namely business architecture, information architecture, and technology architecture [14]. Business architecture defines the business strategy, governance, organization, and key business processes. Information architecture is divided into two sub-layers, namely data architecture and application architecture. A data architecture describes the logical structure of organization and data management. The application architecture provides a blueprint for the application system to be used, Technology Architecture describes the physical realization of a technology architecture that is used.

Research [15] entitled *Achieving Benefits with Enterprise Architecture*, highlights the importance of enterprise architecture service capabilities for an organization so that it can bring benefits to the organization. The benefits of enterprise architecture are achieved through dynamic capabilities that are driven by IT and business. In research on the benefits or advantages of implementing this business architecture, the author does not examine the benefits of business architecture using a particular framework or framework, so that in addition to knowing the benefits of business architecture, it can also be known whether the framework is successfully applied in designing business architecture in an organization. Therefore, in this study, the authors describe the benefits obtained by implementing a business architecture by applying a framework that is the TOGAF framework so that by applying the framework, it gets more specific benefits.

Besides being widely used by industry parties, the TOGAF framework can also be applied to the development of hospital sector enterprise architecture to provide direct and indirect services. The results of an enterprise architecture design research at this hospital state that although there is no enterprise architecture for government organizations and trade centers and service agent frameworks providing all hospital needs [16]. Another finding from this research is to introduce TOGAF as a framework with the highest conformity with business processes in hospitals, which explains the access to business processes in detail so that they can be understood and implemented easily. The success of the implementation of the TOGAF framework in the enterprise architecture development of the hospital sector is a trigger for the authors to prove whether the TOGAF framework was also successfully applied to the development of enterprise architecture in the academic service sector in tertiary institutions.

III. METHOD

1. Research methods

In conducting this research, the authors conducted interviews and direct observations to the research location to obtain information relating to business processes, data/information, applications, and technologies that are being or have been used by organizations. Based on these interviews and observations, there are problems or obstacles that occur to the academic service process at a tertiary institution. Interviews and observations directly intended to obtain information relating to business processes from each of the information systems that exist at this time.

2. Framework used

The framework used to build an enterprise architecture of the academic service system is to use the TOGAF Framework in the preliminary phase until the phase technology architecture, as can be seen in Figure 1. In this

study, the focus is on the design of the academic service system blueprints on data architecture, applications, and technology.

Figure 1. TOGAF Framework

The following explanation is the phase used.

a. Preliminary phase

This is the initial phase to define the research framework, starting from defining the scope of the organization, defining teams and organizations, identifying and setting principles, and selecting and adjusting the architectural framework used.

b. Architecture vision phase

This phase builds uniformity from several views on the needs of enterprise architecture to achieve organizational goals. At this stage, an analysis of strategy needs and the scope of business processes are carried out.

c. Business architecture phase

This stage is to define the initial conditions of the business architecture, mapping the structure of each business model that includes all business activities needed based on the needs, scenario of each business process. The formulation of strategies in architecture vision is carried out using a value chain model.

d. Information system architecture phase

This phase determines how the information system architecture is developed. Activities that include this stage are the creation of data architecture and application architecture that will be used by organizations. Data architecture emphasizes the aspects of the needs of business functions, processes, and services. Whereas application architecture emphasizes the need for information architecture planning of all information processes and services within the scope of the application portfolio that will be generated.

e. Technology architecture phase

The technology architecture emphasizes the technical aspects of the composition of hardware and network technology. This is to ensure the smooth flow and connectedness of all information flowing from each business process within the scope of the portfolio of technologies which includes software and hardware.

3. Research flow

The flow in this research is adjusted to the TOGAF framework so that it can produce an enterprise architecture model of academic services at a tertiary institution. The flow of this research is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Research Flow

IV. RESULT & DISCUSSION

Based on the results of interviews and observations at a tertiary institution, it was found that there was no application of an academic service information system to support academic service activities, so it could not meet the needs of tertiary institutions to gain access to information. To design an academic service system, a framework for modeling enterprise architecture in the form of blueprints is needed that can be used as a reference in the design, construction, and development of systems.

1. Preliminary phase

The preliminary phase is the preparatory activities needed to meet business needs for the new architecture. The first step is to determine the scope of the enterprise. Architectural planning is carried out by raising business processes related to academic services at tertiary institutions, namely the admission of new business processes, academic operational business processes, student graduation business processes, financial business processes, staffing business processes, and facilities and infrastructure business processes. The second step is to define the resources or input needed to support the development of enterprise architecture, namely the vision and mission, the main tasks, the organizational structure of the business, objectives, business processes, and the condition of the systems and technologies that are running. The third stage is determining the framework used. In the development of enterprise architecture using the TOGAF framework that has defined clear principles about the design of enterprise architecture. The fourth stage is carried out implementing architectural tools. At this stage, there has been a match between problem-solving carried out with the organization both in terms of policy and operations.

2. Architecture vision phase

The vision of modeling this academic service system architecture is:

- a. Designing an academic information system that is aligned with the business needs of the organization or university so that it is expected to produce a quality lecture process.
- b. Optimizing the functions of the TOGAF framework to design integrated system recommendations in each business process.

3. Business architecture phase

A good architectural design is a design that can answer problems that are tailored to the vision and mission of the organization. This phase defines the scope of the academic service architecture which aims to understand the conditions that occur in organizations or universities and subsequently made suggestions for improvement by modeling business architecture. Figure 3 is the value chain of academic services at the tertiary institutions and the stakeholders involved, namely the leaders of the tertiary institutions, prospective students, students, educators, and non-educational personnel.

Figure 3. Academic Service System Value Chain

This analysis is carried out using observation, interviews, and study the rules that are following the Standard Operational Procedure (SOP) in universities. Observations were made to obtain problems or obstacles that occur in the main process of academic services, namely new student admission activities, academic operational activities, and student graduation so that solutions to these problems can be found, as described in Table 1.

Table 1. Problems and Solutions to Academic Service Systems

No	Business Activity	Problems	Solutions
1	Admission of new students	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Selection of student admissions is still relatively long 2. The results of student data management still cannot be accessed by the parties concerned quickly 3. The results of the admission of new students are announced in a printed manner so that not all parties get information 	Simplify the process of admitting new students with the help of technology and information systems that are integrated with the database so that the results of new student admissions can be directly accessed by the authorities
2	Academic operational activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The use of information technology is still carried out only to the extent of each work unit 2. The student registration process is still done manually namely recording on the registration book 3. Test administration is not integrated into the system 4. Student academic reporting is done repeatedly 5. Information on payment of tuition fees still requires printed documents from the financial department. 	The need for integration of academic service information systems between work units so that there is no repetition of data collection and the process of operational activities can take place more quickly
3	Student graduation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Registration of student graduation is still done using printed forms and collected directly to the staff. 2. There is a repetition of student data collection even though a college must have student data 3. Must find student data in the financial department to ascertain whether the student has paid tuition fees 4. Must find student data whether they have passed the thesis examination. 5. Alumni data management is still not good 	Providing a student graduation registration system that is connected to the university database server, as well as providing information systems for alumni

4. Information system architecture phase

This phase is the phase to make information systems architecture modeling as the basis for building an integrated academic service information system. This phase is divided into two stages, namely the stages of building application architecture and data architecture.

a. Application architecture

Application architecture discusses the current applications and applications to be designed. The purpose of application architecture is to define the main types of applications needed to process data and manage business functions at tertiary institutions. The proposed application solutions are as in Table 2.

Table 2. Application architecture

Activity Entity	Application Solution
Admission of new students	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. New student registration application 2. College admission test application 3. New student re-registration application 4. Application for reporting new student admissions 5. Build an integrated database so that it can be accessed by other parties
Academic operational activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Student registration application 2. Course scheduling application 3. Academic guidance application 4. Study plan card application 5. Application of student study results
Student graduation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Graduation registration application 2. Application of diplomas and value transcripts 3. Web-based alumni database application 4. Tracer study applications and job vacancies

b. Data architecture

Data architecture aims to define the data requirements that will be used in the application architecture. Identifying candidate data candidates is done to define data architecture. The results of the candidate data analysis can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Data Architecture

Activity Entity	Data Entity Candidates
Admission of new students	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Registration 2. New student admission committee 3. Registration fee 4. Entry selection 5. Prospective students 6. Selection exam material 7. Announcement of graduation 8. Re-register
Academic operational activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. College student 2. Lecturer 3. Majors 4. Courses 5. Curriculum 6. Courses schedule 7. Exam
Student graduation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. College student 2. Alumni 3. Job vacancy

The proposed data entity has attributes and relations that are described using Class Diagrams. The following is a conceptual model of the Class Diagram to describe the entity of new student admission activities, academic operational activities, and student graduation.

Figure 4. Class Diagram of New Student Admission Processes

Figure 5. Class Diagram Process Academic Operational Activities

Figure 6. Class Diagram of Student Graduation Processes

5. Technology architecture phase

This phase makes a proposed technology platform related to the needs of an integrated academic information system at tertiary institutions. Technology architecture is a definition of technology needs that needs to be provided in the business environment to run a data architecture that can manage data based on application architecture. Details of the proposed technology platform for application development are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Proposed Technology Platforms

Type	Device	Amount
Hardware	Personal Computer (PC)	5 units in the academic service room
	Server	1 piece, to store a database that can be accessed by academics, finance, majors and libraries
	Keyboard, mouse, scanner input devices	5 units for the academic section
	Monitor	5 units for the academic section
	Printer	5 units for the academic section
	Hard disk storage media	4 units for the academic section
Software	Operating system	According to the number of PCs and Servers
	Microsoft Excel spreadsheet	5 pieces, according to the number of PCs
	Microsoft word processor	5 pieces, according to the number of PCs
	Internet browser	5 pieces, according to the number of PCs
	Database management system	1 piece, for database server
	Programming language	5 pieces, according to the number of PCs
Data communication	Antivirus	5 pieces, according to the number of PCs
	LAN and Internet networks	Covers all academic sections
	Network equipment such as switches, modems, routers, UTP cables, microphones, and access points	3 modems, 3 switches, 1 router, 3 mikrotik, 3 access points

Figure 7 explains the network computing diagram of the academic service system, which can be accessed through browsers of various technology and communication tools because computer network technology uses the internet network.

Figure 7. Academic Service System Network Computing Diagram

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the discussion delivered by the stages of the study, it can be concluded that the modeling of enterprise architecture in the academic service sector of higher education has been successfully applied using the TOGAF framework by the standards of higher education institutions. This academic service architecture modeling results in improvements or solutions to improve academic service performance so that the problem of the absence of information systems in the organization can be solved with this architecture. The data and information needed can be obtained faster with the presence of information technology because the business processes carried out are also less. From the business architecture phase, it can be seen how the current problem or condition has then sought a solution to solve the problem. In the information system architecture phase, it is obtained the data architecture and application architecture proposed in the academic services section so that the system development becomes more structured. Whereas in the technology architecture phase, the technological requirements needed for academic services are obtained.

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